

HIGH ENTROPY ALLOYS COATINGS: PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14287622>

Abstract: High entropy alloys (HEAs) have been widely applied as a new generation of materials in materials science and coating technologies in recent years. This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the existing problems and prospects of coatings obtained from high entropy alloys. The mechanical, thermal, and corrosion resistance properties of HEAs, as well as the challenges encountered during their preparation and on their surfaces, are discussed in detail. The article addresses the technological problems in the application of HEAs, new methods for improving coating quality, and prospects for future developments. The research findings highlight the potential for effectively utilizing high entropy alloys in various industries.

Keywords: High entropy alloys, coatings, materials science, corrosion, mechanical properties, nanostructures, technological problems.

High entropy alloys (HEAs) are alloys composed of several elements present in high concentrations, distinguishing them from conventional alloys due to their unique physical and chemical properties. As multi-component systems, HEAs possess high mechanical strength, heat resistance, corrosion resistance, and other high-performance characteristics, making them promising materials for various industrial applications. The development of these alloys is bringing revolutionary changes in the field of materials science. However, several technological challenges remain associated with HEAs. Issues such as their production, optimization of mechanical and thermal properties, and ensuring resistance to corrosion and other external influences are still not fully resolved. Particularly, coatings made from HEAs are receiving significant attention in both industrial and scientific research circles because they provide surfaces with high durability and long-term performance. At the same time, the prospects for the development of these materials and new research directions are generating great interest in the fields of materials science and technology [3, 183-202].

High entropy alloys (HEAs) are alloys made from several metal elements, with each component's proportion being equal or relatively high. These

materials typically include five or more primary components, and their composition is optimized to achieve the maximum value of entropy. The main feature of HEAs is their high entropy level, which alters their physical, chemical, and mechanical properties.

Key Characteristics of HEAs:

Characteristic	Description
Multi-component composition	Alloys consisting of five or more metallic elements.
High mechanical properties	Possess high tensile strength, compression, and elongation characteristics
Corrosion resistance	Typically, HEAs have high corrosion resistance.
Heat and cold resistance	Capable of effective operation at high temperatures.

HEAs are widely used in industries that require high performance and long-term operation, including aerospace, energy, and automotive industries. Additionally, the complexities in their production process are being addressed through scientific research.

Although high entropy alloys (HEAs) have wide applications due to their unique physical and chemical properties, there are several challenges in their production and application. HEAs are multi-component alloys, and controlling their composition and phase structures is difficult. While HEAs can operate at high temperatures, their thermal stability depends on phase transformations, segregation, and crystallization processes, which may reduce their mechanical strength and corrosion resistance. Despite their high mechanical properties, the complex structures of HEAs make it challenging to optimize their mechanical characteristics. Some HEAs have good corrosion resistance, but other components, such as nickel-free alloys, may be susceptible to corrosion in humid environments. To enhance corrosion resistance, the need for special protective coatings or the addition of new alloying elements arises. The production technology for HEAs is still in the development stage and requires new technologies. High-temperature melting processes and special equipment increase production costs. HEAs generate significant interest in industry and science, but they face technological challenges [1, 700-704].

New approaches and optimized materials are needed to address these issues. High entropy alloys (HEAs) can also be applied as high-performance coatings due to their unique physical and chemical properties. The multi-component structure of HEAs provides advantages such as high mechanical

strength, heat and cold resistance, and corrosion resistance. However, the use of HEAs as coatings also brings about several technological and production challenges. The high mechanical strength, heat and cold resistance, and corrosion resistance of HEAs make them ideal coating materials. HEAs enriched with nanostructures further improve their tensile strength, corrosion resistance, and thermal stability, making them effective for long-term performance. The high corrosion resistance of HEAs enables their effective use in the oil and gas industry and aerospace industry. Thermal coatings made from HEAs perform well in high-temperature systems and military technologies, withstanding high heat and mechanical stresses. Coatings made from HEAs are used in the automotive and energy industries for their resistance to high heat and mechanical loads. There are technological challenges in producing HEAs and applying coatings effectively. Through scientific research, the efficiency and economic viability of HEAs are continuously improving [6].

High entropy alloys (HEAs) are generating significant interest in industrial technologies due to their unique physical and chemical properties. They possess advantages such as high mechanical strength, heat and cold resistance, and corrosion resistance, making them applicable across various industrial sectors. However, their practical application still requires addressing several challenges. HEAs, with their multi-component composition, form various microstructures that define the material's properties. By managing nanostructure approaches and the interactions between phase systems, the quality of HEAs can be improved. It is essential to optimize the heat and mechanical properties of HEAs, particularly to ensure their long-term performance in high-temperature systems. Improving aspects such as mechanical strength and thermal expansion is also necessary.

To enhance the corrosion resistance of HEAs, it is important to add new elements and develop nano-coating technologies, which will help protect the material over time. Moreover, efforts should be made to make the production processes of HEAs environmentally cleaner and explore recycling possibilities. Sustainable production methods and efficient resource usage will reduce the environmental impact. Developing effective technologies to reduce the complexities in the production process is essential. 3D printing and additive manufacturing technologies may optimize the production process. HEAs are being applied in industries such as aerospace, automotive, and electronics. They provide high resistance to heat and mechanical loads and are also used to enhance the efficiency of electrical conversion and electronic devices. HEAs play

a significant role in materials science and industrial technologies. It is necessary to improve their physical and chemical properties, develop them for new applications, and optimize the production technologies.

Conclusion: High entropy alloys (HEAs) hold significant potential in materials science and industrial technologies due to their unique physical and chemical properties. Their advantages, such as high mechanical strength, heat and cold resistance, and corrosion resistance, make HEAs promising as modern coating materials. However, the application of HEAs requires improvements in microstructure, corrosion resistance, production processes, and environmental characteristics. Coatings made from HEAs are widely used in industries such as aerospace, automotive, and energy.

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